

THE PRACTICE OF WIND ENERGY AND ITS USE AND ITS IMPORTANCE

Nurullayev Orzikul Ubaevich

Jizpi is a senior teacher of the "Electrical Technology" department.

Phone: +998919431810; orziqulnurullayev63@gmail.com

Abstract: Mankind has long used wind energy from hydropower and steam engines. In England, Germany, France, Denmark, the Netherlands, the United States and other countries, wind energy has been used extensively in industry and agriculture. This article discusses the current practice of wind energy and its importance.

Keywords: wind energy, wind generator, power plant, wind turbines, air mass.

The main part The current work on the use of wind energy consists in the creation of separate large-capacity wind generators and the connection of the laming energy to the existing power grids and use as the main grid. The circulation of the air mass around the Earth's atmosphere has been assessed differently by experts [1]. The annual theoretical reserve of winds is 100 times more than all the energy reserves on Earth and is 3300×10^{12} kW·h. But only 10-12% of this energy can be used [2]. For example, in 1987, 10×10^{12} kW·h of energy was generated by all wind turbines on Earth.

produced, that is, only 0.3% of the annual reserve was used.

Wind is the movement of air masses as a result of changes in pressure due to the intensity of sunlight [3]. Economically, the speed of the wind on the ground

If it is not less than 5 m/s, it is advisable to use wind generators. Wind power generators are 2-4 times more expensive than traditional generators. But in some regions where wind energy is constant, it is an important source of energy [4].

Usually, wind energy is determined by the effect of a certain area perpendicular to the wind, i.e.;

$$N_{wind\ current} = 0,0049 \cdot q \cdot V \cdot F$$

Here: q - air density (relative to temperature and atmospheric pressure), kg/m³; V - air flow speed, m/s [5];

F - area surface, m².

The amount of energy transmitted by a wind energy device is fundamentally different from the amount of energy generated by air flow [6]. Because part of the energy of the air flow is wasted in the blades of the wind wheel, reducers and generators. The amount of wasted energy is taken into account by the coefficient of wind energy use. The power of the wind energy device can be calculated by the following formula, defining the surface of the field perpendicular to the wind with the diameter of the wind wheel:

$$N_{\text{candle energy build}} = 0,00386 \cdot q \cdot V \cdot D^2 \cdot \xi_{par} \cdot \eta_{red} \cdot \eta_{gen}.$$

Here: D - working wheel diameter, m;

η_{red} and η_{gen} - useful work coefficients of the reducer and generator;

ξ_{par} - air flow energy wasted in the wings [7].

According to estimates, wind energy efficiency of wind turbines can be as high as 48%, while the overall efficiency of wind turbines is even lower.

Perpendicular to the wind, mainly the blades of wind turbines are located. The power of the wind turbine is determined not by the number of blades, but by the diameter of the impeller. Figure 1 shows the graph of the relationship between the diameter of the impeller of the wind turbine and its power [8].

The power of the wind turbine is directly proportional to the wind speed and inversely proportional to the number of blades of the impeller:

The conversion of mechanical energy generated by air flow into electrical energy is carried out using wind power plants. The sum of several wind turbines forms a wind power plant. The main working part of wind turbines is the wind wheel [8].

Figure 1. A graph of the relationship between the diameter of the impeller of a wind turbine and its power. There are vane, carousel and drum types of windmills [9]. Wind turbines are mainly used in wind turbines, which are the most efficient

Figure 2. Appearance of winged wind wheels: a - two-wheeled; b - three-wheeled; d - four-wheel drive [10]. It should be remembered that the wind current received by the windmill is determined by the diameter of the windmill, the number of blades in it is not important. Currently, there are wind turbines with an impeller diameter of 1-64 m [11]. Most wind generators work with wind speeds above 3-4 m/s. Wind generators will have maximum power with the help of wind blowing at a speed of 8-25 m/s. Usually, the maximum operating speed of wind generators is 25-30 m/s. Wind energy is an environmentally friendly source of energy. But for wind power plants, very large areas are required (wind turbines should be located far from each other and the distance between them should be 6-18 times the diameter

of the impeller). For example, 5-7 km² area is needed for a wind turbine with a working wheel $D = 100$ m. All-in-one wind farm and for that, tens of km² are needed. Another disadvantage is that the working wheel makes noise and vibrates the air, which destroys TV and radio broadcasts [12]. Germany ranks first in the use of wind energy. The production of wind energy in this country is increasing by 500-1500 MW per year, currently the amount of energy produced is 2 mln [13].

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